

SENTENCE BOUNDARY DETECTION FOR MULTILINGUAL
LEGAL TEXT

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ABSTRACT

Sentence Boundary Detection (SBD) is one of the foundational building blocks of Natural Language Processing (NLP), with incorrectly split sentences heavily influencing the output quality of downstream tasks. It is a challenging task for algorithms, especially in the legal domain, considering the complex and different sentence structures used. In this work, we curated a diverse multilingual legal dataset consisting of over 130'000 annotated sentences in 6 languages. Our experimental results show that the performance of existing SBD models is subpar on multilingual legal data. We trained and tested monolingual and multilingual models based on CRF, BiLSTM-CRF, and transformers, demonstrating state-of-the-art performance. We also show that our multilingual models outperform all baselines in the zero-shot setting on a Portuguese test set. For further use and research by the community, we publicly release our dataset, models, and code.

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ACRONYMS

SBD Sentence Boundary Detection

CRF Conditional Random Fields

NN Neural Network

BILSTM Bidirectional LSTM

LSTM Long Short-Term Memory

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

SJP Swiss-Judgement-Prediction

NLP Natural Language Processing

MLP Multi-Legal-File

R Recall

P Precision

F1 F1-Score

RNN Recurrent Neural Network

BERT Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers

INTRODUCTION

Recent methodological advances, e.g., transformers (Vaswani et al., 2017), have led to substantial progress in quality and performance of language models as well as growth in the general field of Natural Language Processing (NLP). This is also seen in legal NLP, with the quantity of research papers increasing drastically in the last few years (Katz et al., 2023).

Not as much attention and resources have been directed to the Sentence Boundary Detection (SBD) task, being viewed as solved by some, as high baseline performances can be achieved by utilizing simple lookup methods capturing frequent sentence-terminating characters such as periods, exclamations marks and question marks combined with hand-crafted rules (Read et al., 2012). This approach is feasible when applied to well-formed and curated text such as news articles. Noisier domain-specific data containing differently structured text combined with the ambiguity of many sentence-terminating characters (Gillick, 2009; Kiss and Strunk, 2006) – e.g., the period occurring in abbreviations, ellipses, initials etc. as a non-terminating character – often overwhelm the aforementioned methods and also more complicated off-the-shelf SBD systems. This has been illustrated in a number of specific SBD applications such as user-generated content (Gimpel et al., 2011; Read et al., 2012) as well as in the clinical (Newman-Griffis et al., 2016) and financial domain (Du, Huang, and Moilanen, 2019; Mathew and Guggilla, 2019).

In legal documents, the aforementioned difficulties are increased with legal text consisting of smaller parts such as paragraphs, clauses etc., making it quite different from standard text. Furthermore, sentences are long and may contain complex structures such as citations, parentheses, and lists. These structures are often utilized to convey additional information to the reader (e.g., citations referencing another text) or formatting the text in a specific way (e.g., lists emphasizing ideas or increasing the readability of long paragraphs). However, these structures or special sentences do not follow a standard sentence structure, thus posing an additional challenge to SBD systems, illustrated in several works on English (Sanchez, 2019; Savelka et al., 2017) and German (Glaser, Moser, and Matthes, 2021) legal documents.

Motivation

SBD is often the initial pre-processing step required for further NLP analysis of text. Therefore, it is vital to have a solid SBD system in place to dampen the propagation of errors into higher-level text processing tasks, lowering the overall performance. An important example of such a task is found in the curation of the EUROPARL corpus (Koehn, 2005), a collection of the proceedings of the European Parliament in over 20 languages, for research in statistical machine translation. To create language translation pairs, Koehn (2005) had to align the same sentences in both languages, making it necessary to split the text into sentences beforehand. In their work, they mention the difficulty of SBD, requiring specialized tools for each language, which were not readily available for all languages. Suboptimal SBD most likely weakens the performance of the sentence alignment algorithm and therefore the overall quality of the corpus. A high-quality SBD system, especially one adapted to the legal domain and language, could improve the quality by a large margin. Other examples of NLP tasks where SBD plays a critical role, can be found in text summarization, Part-of-Speech-Tagging and Named Entity Recognition, all very pertinent to the legal domain.

Main Research Questions

In this work, we pose and examine three main research questions:

- RQ1: What is the performance of existing SBD systems on legal data in French, Italian, Spanish, English, and German?
- RQ2: To what extent can we improve upon this performance by training mono- and multilingual models based on CRF, BiLSTM-CRF, and transformers?
- RQ3: What is the performance of the multilingual models on previously unseen Portuguese legal text, i.e., a zero-shot experiment?

Contributions

The contributions of this paper are twofold:

1. We curate and publicly release a large, diverse, high-quality, multilingual legal dataset (see Section 3) containing over 130'000 annotated sentence spans for further research in the community.
2. Using this dataset, we showcase that existing SBD systems exhibit sub-optimal performance on legal text in French, Italian, Spanish, English and German. We train and evaluate state-of-the-art monolingual SBD models based on Conditional Random

Fields (CRF), Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM)-CRF and transformers, achieving F1-scores up to 99.6%. We showcase the performance and feasibility of multilingual SBD models i.e., trained on all languages, achieving F1-scores in the higher nineties, comparable or better than our monolingual models on each aforementioned language. In a zero-shot experiment, we demonstrate that it is possible to achieve good cross-lingual transfer by testing the multilingual models on previously unseen Portuguese legal text. We publicly release all of our monolingual and multilingual models (see Section 6) as well as our code for further use in the community.

RELATED WORK

In this section, we discuss the literature at our disposal. First, we look at works showcasing the need for more research in regard to SBD. Second, we take a look at research tackling the problem of SBD in legal text in several languages.

Read et al. (2012) questioned the status quo of SBD being "solved", especially in more informal language and special domains, by reviewing the current state-of-the-art SBD systems on English news articles and user-generated content. The systems were able to reach F1-scores in the higher nineties for the former, however the performance on user-generated content weakened perceptibly with scores down to the lower nineties, showcasing the need for "a renewed research interest in this foundational first step in NLP." (Read et al., 2012)

2.1 SBD IN THE LEGAL DOMAIN

Savelka et al. (2017) continued this research in the English language by curating a legal dataset, consisting of adjudicatory decisions from the United States. When testing existing systems on the dataset, they report F1-scores between 75% and 78%. Training or adapting these systems to the dataset improved their F1 score to the mid-eighties, which is still lower than their respective performance in more formal domains (Read et al., 2012), showcasing the subpar performance of state-of-the-art SBD in the English legal domain. To improve this issue, they trained a number of CRF models as well as a model based on hand-crafted rules, reporting F1-scores of 79% for the hand-crafted model and up to 96% for the CRFs. Sanchez (2019) experimented on the same dataset and report an F1-score of 74% when utilizing the Punkt Model (Kiss and Strunk, 2006), adapting this model to the dataset improved the performance slightly. Additionally, they trained and evaluated CRF and Neural Network (NN) models, reporting F1-scores up to 98.5% and 98.4% respectively. Our multilingual models achieve F1-scores between 95.1% and 97% on the same dataset. Savelka et al. (2017) also developed a publicly available, comprehensive and widely used set of annotation-guidelines regarding the annotation of sentence boundaries in legal texts. We used their work as a foundation for our guidelines.

Similarly, Glaser, Moser, and Matthes (2021) curated a German legal dataset, split into laws and judgements; a similar distribution is used in our work. They established a baseline performance of existing SBD systems and compared it to CRF and NN models trained on

the aforementioned dataset. Their findings outline F1-scores between 70% to 78% for off-the-shelf systems, supporting the view that the performance of existing SBD system is subpar on legal data. The CRFs and NNs models achieve F1-scores up to 98.5%. However, a significant decrease in performance was reported, when applying them to previously unseen German legal texts with scores down to 81.1%. Our multilingual models showcase F1-scores between 91.6% to 97.6% on the German dataset.

2.2 SBD IN OTHER DOMAINS

In the financial domain, Du, Huang, and Moilanen (2019) experimented with BiLSTM models combined with a CRF layer as well as the transformer-based model BERT (Devlin et al., 2019) and compared their performance, approaching SBD as a sequence labelling task to extract useful sentences from noisy financial texts. They demonstrate that BERT significantly outperforms BiLSTM-CRFs across all evaluation metrics, including F1-scores. In their work they also underline the fact that "SBD has received much less attention in the last few decades than some of the more popular subtasks and topics in NLP." (Du, Huang, and Moilanen, 2019),

Schweter and Ahmed (2019) compared the performance of Long Short-Term Memorys (LSTMs), BiLSTMs and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to OpenNLP¹ in an SBD task on the Europarl², SETimes³ and Leipzig Corpora⁴ containing around 10 different languages, showcasing the use of their models as robust, language-independent SBD systems.

¹ <https://opennlp.apache.org/>

² <https://www.statmt.org/europarl/>

³ <https://opus.nlp.eu/SETIMES.php>

⁴ <https://corpora.uni-leipzig.de/en>

DATASET

In an effort to create a diverse set of multilingual legal data and obtain an in-depth look at the performance of legal SBD in a multitude of languages, we have annotated sentence spans for three distinct datasets, one each for French, Italian, and Spanish. Each dataset contains around 20,000 sentences, split evenly between judgements and laws, chosen to capture a diverse selection of different areas of law. The laws contain the Constitution, part of the Civil Code as well as part of the Criminal Code. Since the Constitution is a relatively small subset, it was used for evaluation only. The judgements contain court decisions from various sources and legal areas. Furthermore, we have annotated a smaller Portuguese dataset containing around 1800 sentences, with the same relative subsets as described above. This dataset was used for zero-shot experiments. Additionally, we in-

Figure 1: Sentence length distribution in tokens

tegrated two publicly available datasets, an English collection of legal texts (Savelka et al., 2017), consisting of Adjudicatory Decision from the United States as well as a German dataset (Glaser, Moser, and Matthes, 2021), comprising laws and judgements, into our dataset to further increase its diversity.

The sentence length distribution of our dataset is illustrated in Fig. 1, showcasing the relative frequency of sentence length in tokens for laws and judgements, with a bin size of 5. The sentences were tokenized using an aggressive tokenizer, described further below, resulting in a larger amount of tokens per sentences than usual.¹ We do

¹ Sentences with token length one stem from single token sentences such as the headline "Facts".

Table 1: Statistics on datasets per language and subset

Language	Subset	Sentences	Tokens	# of Documents	Source
French	Judgements	9971	342469	315	Swiss-Judgement-Prediction (SJP)
	Laws	11055	334453	3	Wipolex
Italian	Judgements	10129	340041	183 + 60	SJP + Multi-Legal-Pile (MLP)
	Laws	10849	301466	3	Jus.unitn.it
Spanish	Judgements	10656	356681	20 + 84	Wipolex + Multi-Legal-Pile
	Laws	11501	229240	3	Wipolex
Portuguese	Judgements	759	20590	6	Wipolex
	Laws	1010	25947	3	Wipolex
German	Judgements	21409	506009	131	Glaser, Moser, and Matthes (2021)
	Laws	20330	484816	13	Glaser, Moser, and Matthes (2021)
English	Judgements	25899	712433	80	Savelka et al. (2017)
Total	Laws & Judgments	133568	3654145	906	

not show sentences longer than 101 tokens for clarity’s sake, with only 2634 sentences being longer than that. The longest sentence in our dataset is 2412 tokens.

Selected statistics and information about the dataset are provided in Table 1 and links to our data sources are listed in Appendix i. The dataset is publicly available on [HuggingFace](#).

3.1 ANNOTATION

The human annotator was tasked with correcting the sentence-spans predicted by an automatic SBD system² (Savelka et al., 2017) based on CRF, which was trained on data annotated using annotation guidelines by Savelka et al. (2017). This helped improve the quality and consistency of our annotations. Furthermore, a practical rule set, heavily influenced by the aforementioned guidelines, was utilized to aid the annotator in the annotation process, reducing the complexity of the task and helped provide dependable and well-founded data. The rule set is outlined in Section 3.1.1, containing the most important sentence structures followed an example.

The documents were annotated using Prodigy³. Because Prodigy requires pre-tokenized text, a customized tokenizer was applied to the input text, further described in Section 3.2. The decision to annotate the full sentence-span, in lieu of just the first and last token in the sequence, was made to incentivize the annotator to read the text instead of skimming it for sentence-terminating characters. To make the annotation easier, laws were split into smaller chunks with one to three articles per chunk, while judgements were only split, if they surpassed ~15000 characters since Prodigy was unable to handle longer documents.

² https://github.com/jsavelka/luima_sbd

³ <https://prodi.gy/>

3.1.1 Legal Sentence Structures

In this section, we briefly describe the most important sentence structures in legal text, heavily influenced by Savelka et al. (2017), followed by an example in French.

STANDARD SENTENCE have subject, object and verb in the correct order and the last token in the sequence is a sentence-terminating character.

- *Il s'est établi comme ingénieur indépendant.*

LINGUISTICALLY TRANSFORMED SENTENCE are similar to a standard sentence, but slight transformations such as changes to the word order are applied.

- *Tout porte à croire, en réalité, qu'elle est condamnée au surendettement, puis à la faillite.*

HEADLINES determine the structure of the text and show relatedness between parts of the document and therefore convey important information about the overall structure of the text.

- *Considérant en fait et en droit*
- *Article 9-1*
- *PAR CES MOTIFS*
- *DÉCLARATION*

DATA FIELDS provide the name and data of a field. This is annotated as a sentence, for example in English "Civil Chamber: Madrid" has a similar meaning to "The civil chambers are located in Madrid".

- *Numéro d'appel: 1231/2015*
- *Date: 11/06/2020*

PARENTHESES appear frequently in legal text, often combined with citations. We annotate parentheses with the sentence they belong to. Sentences inside the parentheses are not annotated separately. The following example is a single sentence.

- *Ce dernier étant domicilié à l'étranger, il ne peut en effet prétendre à des mesures de réadaptation (art. 8a 1er paragraphe. Convention de sécurité sociale entre la Suisse et la Yougoslavie du 8 juin 1962).*

COLONS should not be annotated as a sentence-terminating character, unless the sequence ends with a colon immediately followed by a newline. The reasoning here is that a sequence ending in a colon followed by a line break usually introduce a list or block quote, which should be annotated separately to the introductory sentence.

LISTS are annotated differently depending on its type. For lists with incomplete sentences as list items, often ended with a semi-colon, the whole list is annotated as a sentence. The following example consists of 2 sentences, the introductory sentence to the colon and 1° to the period.

- *Au cours du délai fixé par la juridiction pour accomplir un travail d'intérêt général, le condamné doit, outre l'obligation d'accomplir le travail prescrit, satisfaire aux mesures de contrôle suivantes:*
 1° *Répondre aux convocations du juge de l'application des peines ou du travailleur social désigné;*
 2° *Se soumettre à l'examen médical préalable à l'exécution de la peine qui a pour but de rechercher s'il n'est pas atteint d'une affection dangereuse pour les autres travailleurs et de s'assurer qu'il est médicalement apte au travail auquel il est envisagé de l'affecter.*

However, if the list items themselves are sentences, the list number or letter and the list items are both annotated as one sentence each, the reason being that list number and item express separate thoughts. In the example below we have 3 sentences (introductory, list number, list item).

- *Considérant en droit:*
 1.- *En instance fédérale, peut seul être examiné le point de savoir si la commission de recours a exigé à bon droit de la recourante une avance de frais de 500 fr. pour la procédure de recours de première instance.*

ELLIPSES are used to indicate when part of a sentence or part of the document are left out. The following example shows the use cases for ellipses. The first ellipsis is annotated separately, as it indicates sentences that are missing. The second ellipses indicates, that part of that single sentence was left out and is therefore not annotated separately.

- (...) *La faute de X. est d'une exceptionnelle gravité tant les faits qui lui sont reprochés (...), commis avec une certaine froideur sont insoutenables et comportent un caractère insupportable pour les victimes.*

FOOTNOTES / ENDNOTES convey additional information to the reader.

Indicators for end- and footnotes such as numbers or letters should always be annotated as being inside the sentence span, even if they occur after the sentence-terminating character. As an example, the sequence below is just one sentence, with "[2]" as the indicator:

- *La loi ne dispose que pour l'avenir; elle n'a point d'effet rétroactif. [2]*

Furthermore, endnotes appearing as numbered lists, should be annotated as following the guidelines for lists. In the example below, (2) is one sentence, followed by a normal sentence:

- (2) Le remplacement des membres du Parlement a lieu conformément aux dispositions de l'article 25.

3.2 TOKENIZER

We implemented an aggressive tokenizer based on Regex to segment text into tokens, also employed in other research (Glaser, Moser, and Matthes, 2021; Savelka et al., 2017). The same tokenizer was utilized for all languages. Words, numbers and special characters such as new-lines and whitespace are separated into individual sequences. This was done to ensure no information (e.g., a line break indicating a sentence boundary), vital to the SBD process, was lost. An example is showcased below; tokenized whitespace is left out for clarity's sake:

- *D. _ est entré à l'école le 16 juillet 1979.*
- *D | . | _ | est | entré | à | l | ' | école | le | 16 | juillet | 1979 |*
.

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN & EVALUATION

We conducted a series of experiments to answer our research questions posed in Section 1. Firstly, we compared selected existing models to establish a baseline performance. Secondly, we trained and evaluated a multitude of monolingual and multilingual models based on CRF, BiLSTM-CRF and transformers and compared them to the baseline. Lastly, we evaluated the performance of the multilingual models on previously unseen data in a zero-shot experiment.

4.1 BASELINE MODELS

We evaluated several popular existing models based on different technologies, consisting of NLTK, CoreNLP, Stanza, and Spacy as baselines. We further describe each model below.

4.1.1 *NLTK*

A fully unsupervised SBD system created by Kiss and Strunk (2006). The main thought behind the system is that most falsely predicted sentence boundaries stem from periods after abbreviations. The system therefore discovers abbreviations by looking at the length, the collocational bond, internal periods and occurrences of abbreviations without an ending period of each token in the text. We test a pre-trained model as well as a model trained on our data.

4.1.2 *CoreNLP*

A rule-based system from the Stanford CoreNLP toolkit (Manning et al., 2014). This system is based on triggering events such as periods, question marks or exclamation marks to predict sentence boundaries.

4.1.3 *Stanza*

A multilingual system based on a BiLSTM model (Qi et al., 2020). We only use the first part of its NLP pipeline, the tokenizer. It looks at tokenization and sentence splitting jointly, recognizing it as a problem regarding the tagging of character sequences. The model therefore predicts whether a given character is the end of a token or the end of a sentence.

4.1.4 *Spacy*

A multilingual system (Honnibal et al., 2020) featuring pre-trained models using different technologies such as CNN and transformers. For our purposes, only the first part of its toolkit (tokenizer and sentence splitter) was used.

4.2 TRAINED MODELS

Following the works presented in Section 2, we chose to test models based on CRFs, BiLSTM-CRFs and transformers. We further describe these models in more detail in the following subsections. For testing, we trained and evaluated monolingual models for each language as well as multilingual models using all languages except Portuguese, once for laws, once for judgements and both types together.

4.2.1 *Conditional Random Fields*

The tokenizer described in Subsection 3.2 was used to tokenize the input text, including whitespaces. Each token is then translated into a list of relatively simple features, which represent the token. Additionally, for each token we add the features of tokens in a pre-defined window around the token; the size of each window is variable for each feature. Our chosen features and window-sizes are inspired by Glaser, Moser, and Matthes (2021) and Savelka et al. (2017), further described in Table 2. A sample representation is showcased in Appendix i.

We used the "BIOES" labeling system to label the input data, following Lin et al. (2020): "B-Sentence" and "L-Sentence" denote the first and last token in the sequence, while tokens inside and outside the sequence are denoted by "I-Sentence" and "O" respectively. "U" is for sequences consisting of one token.

For training our CRF models, we used the `python-crfsuite`¹ implementation. We trained each model for 100 iterations, with regularization parameters of 1 and $1e^{-3}$ for C1 and C2 respectively, L-BFGS for the algorithm and the inclusion of all possible feature transitions set to true.

4.2.2 *Bidirectional LSTM - CRF*

A BiLSTM connects two LSTMs with opposite directions to the same output, allowing it to capture information from past and future states at the same time. The outputs of each LSTM are concatenated into a representation of each input token. For a BiLSTM-CRF model, a CRF

¹ <https://pypi.org/project/python-crfsuite/>

Table 2: Description of CRF-Features

Feature	Description	Window
Special	Each token is categorized using the following translation: Sentence-terminating tokens as "End", opening and closing parentheses as "Open" and "Close" respectively, newline characters as "Newline", abbreviation characters as "Abbr" and the rest as "No".	10
Lowercase	The token in lowercase.	7
Length	The length of the token.	7
Signature	Each character is represented using the following translation: Lower case and upper case character are rewritten as "c" and "C" respectively, digits are written as "N" and special characters as "S".	5
Lower	Whether the first character is lower case.	3
Upper	Whether the first character is upper case.	3
Digit	Whether the token is a digit.	3

layer is connected to the output of the BiLSTM network, using the aforementioned representation as features to predict the final label.

We utilized the Bi-LSTM-CRF² library to train our models. We used a word embedding dimension of 128, hidden dimension of 256 and a maximum sequence length of 512. The batch-size was 16 with a learning rate of 0.01 and a weight decay of 0.0001. We trained each model for 8 epochs and saved the model with the smallest validation loss. We extracted word embeddings for training from our documents. To label the training data, we utilized the "BILOU" labeling system described in Section 4.2.1. For training, gold sentences were put together into batches with a token-limit of 512 to simulate longer paragraphs.

² <https://github.com/jidasheng/bi-lstm-crf>

4.2.3 *Transformer*

Transformers are a type of NN that utilizes self-attention mechanisms to weigh the importance of different parts of the input when making predictions. Transformer models such as BERT use a multi-layer encoder (Vaswani et al., 2017) to pre-train deep bidirectional representations by jointly conditioning on both left and right context across all layers (Devlin et al., 2019). Thus, we can fine-tune transformer models to the SBD task by adding an additional output layer. In our case we used a pre-trained model³ based on DistilBERT (Sanh et al., 2019), a smaller, more lightweight version of BERT, for all languages on our SBD task.⁴ We trained the models using PyTorch⁵ and Accelerate⁶ with the Adam optimizer for 5 epochs with a batch-size of 8 and learning rate of $2e^{-5}$. We utilized the "BIO" labeling system to label the input tokens.

A limitation of DistilBERT is the input length limit of 512 tokens because the runtime of the self-attention mechanism scales quadratically with the sequence length. This issue is exacerbated, since DistilBERT relies on a WordPiece Tokenizer (Song et al., 2020), splitting the text into subwords resulting in a higher token count per sequence. Thus, to get around the 512 token-limit, each document was split into sentences using the gold annotation. Each consecutive sentence was added to a collection until the total length was as close to the token-limit as possible. Next, the model predicted the sentence boundaries for each collection. Sentences longer than 512 tokens were truncated.⁷ An obvious downside to this solution is that the input text already has to be split into sentences or short sections, which makes it a lot more cumbersome to apply BERT based models directly to unknown text.

For future work, it would be interesting to see, whether it is feasible to chain SBD models (i.e., first, apply a CRF model on the input text to split the text into sections smaller than 512 tokens and second apply a transformer based model). Another solution might be using pre-trained transformer models that support longer input text utilizing an attention mechanism scaling linearly with sequence length, such as LongFormers (Beltagy, Peters, and Cohan, 2020).⁸

³ <https://huggingface.co/distilbert-base-multilingual-cased>

⁴ For efficiency and expediency, we used a smaller model; a bigger model is advisable for future work.

⁵ <https://pytorch.org/>

⁶ <https://huggingface.co/docs/accelerate/index>

⁷ This led to some wrongly predicted sentence boundaries, however this only occurred a few times and is therefore insignificant to the overall score.

⁸ Unfortunately, to the best of our knowledge, so far there do not exist multilingually pretrained efficient transformer models.

4.3 EVALUATION

A characteristic of the SBD task is the inherent imbalance towards non-sentence boundary labels, as each sentence can at most have two sentence boundaries. Thus, to more accurately score our models, we used commonly utilized measures to evaluate our models - Precision (P), Recall (R) and F₁-Score (F₁).

For the evaluation process, we let models predict the sentence spans of every document. These annotated spans are tokenized by our tokenizer (Subsection 3.2). Each token is then assigned a binary value, depending on whether it was a sentence boundary or not. This decouples the predicted sentence spans or boundaries from the tokenizer used, as the tokenizer of some models might designate a slightly different token as the first or last in a sentence, further described in the following example in French: "*C'est en outre ...*". While our tokenizer would designate "C" as the first token in the sequence, a different tokenizer might designate "C'" or even "C'est". This would lead to a wrongly predicted sentence boundary when compared to the gold annotations, although the prediction was actually correct.

The true and predicted labels are gathered for every document type and then compared using Scikit-Learn⁹, calculating the binary F₁-Score. Finally, the scores are averaged for each subset, with Criminal Code, Civil Code and Constitution being reported under "Laws" and the various court decisions under "Judgements".

For each language, the dataset is split into three parts: train, test and validation. The test and validation splits each contain 20% of the dataset. Every model is trained on the train split, and we report their performance on the test split.

We trained each CRF model once and the BiLSTM-CRF and transformer models 5 times with random seeds, reporting the mean performance including standard deviation. If not specified differently, reported values are binary F₁-scores.

⁹ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

INVESTIGATING MODEL TECHNOLOGY

In this chapter, we will take a deeper look at the technology behind our chosen trained models, including CRF, BiLSTM-CRF and transformers.

5.1 CONDITIONAL RANDOM FIELDS

CRF (Lafferty, McCallum, and Pereira, 2001) are often applied to solve a multitude of different tasks e.g. text processing, image segmentation etc. with sequential input data. CRF are based on an undirected graphical model, containing nodes i.e. tokens in the SBD task and edges i.e. dependencies between nodes. Each node has a set of features, basically a representation of the node, further explained in the next section. A simple illustration of a CRF network for sequence tagging is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: CRF Network (Huang, Xu, and Yu, 2015)

To find the unknown label for a node, the model looks not only at the features of the node itself, but also at its neighbouring nodes i.e. nodes that are connected to it, a trait special to CRFs. In our case, we will use a linear-chain CRF, linear in the sense that each node only depends on directly connected nodes and their direct neighbours. Therefore, to find the hidden label for a node, we have to solve the conditional probability $p(y|x)$ i.e. the probability of any particular label y , given the node x :

$$p(y_{1:N}|x_{1:N}) = \frac{1}{Z(x, w)} \exp \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^F \lambda_i f_i(y_{1:n}, x_{1:N}, n) \quad (1)$$

f_i is called a feature function. It is a specific measure of the "compatibility" of the node x and the label y , where each feature function measures a separate type of compatibility. The parameter λ_i reports the weight of the feature function, taking on values between 1 and -1 , with 1 meaning y is extremely likely to be the true label of x and -1

Listing 1: Code sample for "Special" feature function

```

1   def isSpecial(self, token: str) -> str:
      if len(token) > 1 or token.isalnum():
          return "No"
      elif token in ["'"]:
          return 'Abbr'
6   elif token in ['.', '!', '?', ':']:
          return 'End'
      elif token in ['(', '[', '{']:
          return 'Open'
      elif token in [')', ']', '}']:
11  return 'Close'
      elif token in ['\r', '\n']:
          return 'Newline'
      else:
          return 'S'

```

the opposite. Training a CRF basically means learning the parameters or weight λ of each feature function f using an training algorithm. In our case, we use the 'L-BFGS' algorithm (Xiao, Wei, and Wang, 2008) to calculate the gradient descent.

Feature functions or features are an essential component of CRF. They translate the properties of a node into information usable by the model. As an input, they take a set of nodes $x_{1:N}$ and the position of the current node n i.e. the position the current token in the text, and output a boolean or string. Which node properties are important, and therefore need a feature function, can be decided depending on the task at hand. For the SBD task, we defined a multitude of simple feature functions to represent each token. We take a closer look at the "Special" function, which categorizes each node in Listing 1. This feature functions checks whether the token is a special character and if so, what kind and returns it as a string. All feature functions used in our work are presented in more detail in Table 2. For each node, we calculate these properties for the node itself as well as neighbouring nodes in a defined window for each feature function, representing the node. A sample representation can be found in Appendix i.

5.2 BIDIRECTIONAL LSTM - CRF

A LSTM (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997) is a type of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), operating on sequential data. They use a sequence of vectors as input and return another sequence as output, representing information about the sequence for every step in the input. An issue with RNNs is learning long dependencie as they are more biased towards more recent inputs in the sequence (Bengio, Simard, and Frasconi, 1994). LSTMs attempt to solve this issue

by using purpose-built memory cells (Fig. 3), replacing hidden layer updates.

Figure 3: LSTM memory cell (Graves and Schmidhuber, 2005)

Fig. 4 illustrates a LSTM sequence tagging model, utilizing the LSTM memory cell (dashed boxes). For a given sequence, an LSTM

Figure 4: LSTM Network (Huang, Xu, and Yu, 2015)

calculates a representation of the left context (or forward) of the sequence at every word. Using a second LSTM, reading the same sequence in reverse, we also generate a representation of the right context (or backwards), thus being able to access forward and backward information. This kind of network is called a Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM). A word is then represented by a concatenation of its left and right context representation, which is useful information for tagging applications such as our SBD task. For the BiLSTM-CRF model, we add an additional CRF layer to the BiLSTM network output. Instead of manually deciding on specific feature functions to calculate the representation of the current word, the CRF layer utilizes the aforementioned concatenation predicted by the BiLSTM to predict the tag of the current word. An illustration of a BiLSTM-CRF network as a sequence tagging model is shown in Fig. 5.

5.3 TRANSFORMER

Transformers are a type of NN, designed to process sequential input data, however unlike RNNs, LSTMs, etc., transformers process the en-

Figure 5: Bidirectional LSTM - CRF Network (Huang, Xu, and Yu, 2015)

tire input sequence at once, rather than word by word. This alleviates or even solves the long dependency issue, occurring in RNN, LSTMs etc. The input text is tokenized into tokens and then converted via a word embedding into a vector. Transformer architectures have an encoder-decoder structure illustrated in Fig. 6, encoder in the left half, decoder in the right half.

Figure 6: Transformer Architecture (Vaswani et al., 2017)

The encoder has 6 identical layers with two sub-layers, the first is a multi-head self-attention mechanism, the second a simple, position-wise fully connected feed-forward network. Around each of the two sub-layers is a residual connection (He et al., 2016), followed by layer normalization (Ba, Kiros, and Hinton, 2016). The decoder also has 6 identical layers, similar to the encoder, but adds a third sub-layer, performing multi-head attention over encoder-output. In our work, we only use the encoder part as our task does not require the decoder.

A key characteristic of a transformer model is the attention mechanism, called Scaled Dot-Product Attention, illustrated in Fig. 7. As an input, we have matrices of queries Q , keys K and values V , mapping the queries and key-value pair to an output. The output is the weighted sum of the values, with the value weight being a compatibility function of the query and the key.

Scaled Dot-Product Attention

Figure 7: Scaled Dot-Product Attention (Vaswani et al., 2017)

The attention function is shown in Equation 2, with d_k being the dimension of the query and key vectors, computing the dot products of the queries and keys, divided by $\sqrt{d_k}$ and applying a softmax function to obtain the value weights.

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (2)$$

Instead of a single attention function, transformers linearly project the queries, keys and values h times with different, learned linear projections, performing the attention function in parallel. This yields d_v -dimensional output values, which are concatenated and projected, outputting the final values. This mechanism is called multi-head attention, shown in Fig. 8, allowing the model to jointly attend to information for different representation subspaces at different positions. (Vaswani et al., 2017)

The transformer architecture explained above was first implemented by Vaswani et al. (2017). Building on this work, Devlin et al. (2019) released Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT), a multi-layer bidirectional transformer using bidirectional self-attention. Pre-trained BERT models can be fine-tuned to a wide variety of tasks with just one additional output layer, making the use of transformers quite easy. One caveat of transformer models is the token-limit of the input sequence, defined during training of the pre-trained model, mostly set to 512 tokens. This limit is in place, as the runtime of the self-attention mechanism scales quadratically with the input length.

Figure 8: Multi-Head Attention (Vaswani et al., 2017)

Further works, such as Beltagy, Peters, and Cohan (2020), seek to alleviate this issue by using an attention mechanism which scales linearly with input length.

RESULTS

6.1 BASELINE MODELS

The performance of the baseline models described in Section 4 on each language in our dataset is summarized in the upper section of Table 3. A more detailed account for each language and baseline model is shown in Appendix i.

The results for the baseline models are clearly lower than the reported scores for user-generated content by Read et al. (2012), supporting the hypothesis that the performance of out-of-the-box models is subpar on legal data for all tested languages. The difference in performance could be explained in one part by the special sentence structures presented in Section 3.1, while the challenging nature of legal text accounts for another part.

Of interest is the gap between NLTK and NLTK-train in most languages, as training NLTK improves its ability to recognize and correctly predict abbreviations. This showcases that abbreviations are one part of the challenging nature of legal texts. To note here is that Spacy uses a slightly different notion of a sentence compared to the other models: Usually, when two sentences are separated by a newline character, the newline character would not be part of any sentence span, however Spacy would include it in the span of the second sentence. This leads to a false prediction, even though Spacy correctly recognized that there are two sentences. Therefore, the scores Spacy achieves are lower than expected.

Table 3: Mean (\pm std) F1 Score of baseline and multilingual models on all languages and the Portuguese zero-shot experiment. Best scores are in bold.

Language Model	French		Spanish		Italian		English	German		Portuguese (Zero-shot)	
	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Laws
CoreNLP	74.7	76.7	71.4	89.0	79.8	75.6	81.7	69.0	64.0	-	-
NLTK	72.5	75.8	70.2	89.2	72.3	66.3	77.2	72.3	73.8	64.9	57.0
NLTK-train	82.9	75.8	72.1	81.6	84.8	77.5	84.9	74.2	73.5	71.7	64.3
Spacy	86.6	67.2	60.0	70.3	73.9	73.7	79.7	87.5	67.0	59.0	77.7
Stanza	81.9	81.0	83.2	90.2	85.7	87.4	92.3	72.6	64.7	88.6	73.4
CRF	97.8	98.1	94.8	98.9	97.3	97.7	95.1	95.2	91.6	90.2	78.6
BiLSTM-CRF	97.6 \pm 0.3	98.5 \pm 0.2	97.3 \pm 0.1	99.3 \pm 0.2	97.8 \pm 0.1	99.2 \pm 0.1	95.4 \pm 0.3	97.2 \pm 0.2	97.5 \pm 0.5	93.0 \pm 0.6	73.2 \pm 3.3
transformer	98.3 \pm 0.1	98.1 \pm 0.2	97.8 \pm 0.1	99.0 \pm 0.0	98.3 \pm 0.1	99.1 \pm 0.1	97.0 \pm 0.1	92.9 \pm 0.2	97.6 \pm 0.1	93.6 \pm 0.3	91.3 \pm 1.1

Table 4: Mean (\pm std) F1 Score of monolingual models on their respective language. Best scores are in bold.

Language		French		Spanish		Italian		English	German	
Model	Type Trained on	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Judg.	Laws
CRF	Judg.	97.9	73.2	97.0	98.3	98.5	95.6	96.8	97.8	76.5
	Laws	78.5	98.8	54.3	99.6	88.6	99.6	-	75.8	97.7
	Laws + Judg.	97.8	98.8	97.0	99.5	98.3	99.5	-	97.2	97.2
BiLSTM-CRF	Judg.	97.3 \pm 0.3	56.7 \pm 3.0	94.7 \pm 0.5	92.1 \pm 0.9	95.9 \pm 0.3	71.3 \pm 2.2	97.3\pm0.4	97.0 \pm 0.3	76.9 \pm 0.4
	Laws	66.1 \pm 4.2	97.9 \pm 0.2	43.4 \pm 6.8	98.7 \pm 0.2	74.1 \pm 1.2	98.4 \pm 0.2	-	71.9 \pm 2.5	97.3 \pm 0.3
	Laws + Judg.	97.0 \pm 0.4	98.1 \pm 0.1	95.6 \pm 0.5	98.9 \pm 0.4	96.2 \pm 0.2	98.2 \pm 0.1	-	97.2 \pm 0.2	97.6 \pm 0.2
transformer	Judg.	98.2 \pm 0.1	84.7 \pm 1.2	96.9 \pm 0.2	96.9 \pm 0.4	97.8 \pm 0.2	81.8 \pm 0.9	96.5 \pm 0.1	98.0 \pm 0.2	87.2 \pm 0.4
	Laws	92.4 \pm 0.5	97.6 \pm 0.4	89.5 \pm 0.6	97.1 \pm 3.7	89.4 \pm 0.7	98.8 \pm 0.5	-	89.4 \pm 0.5	97.4 \pm 0.1
	Laws + Judg.	98.4\pm0.1	98.2 \pm 0.2	97.3 \pm 0.1	99.0 \pm 0.1	97.1 \pm 0.3	99.1 \pm 0.1	-	98.3\pm0.1	97.5 \pm 0.2

6.2 MONOLINGUAL MODELS

We report the performance of our trained monolingual models in Table 4. Each model was trained and tested on the same language. A more detailed account is shown in Appendix i.

We observe that the performance of each model, when applied to the subset they were trained on, reaches the higher nineties for almost all languages, which is a large improvement over the baseline models from Section 6.1, comparable to the reported performance of SBD systems on English news articles (Read et al., 2012). Our models also perform similarly to the reported performance of CRFs and CNNs on the English (Sanchez, 2019; Savelka et al., 2017) as well as CRFs and NNs on the German dataset (Glaser, Moser, and Matthes, 2021).

Comparing the performance of the models when trained on one subset and evaluated on the other unseen set, i.e. a zero-shot experiment, the transformer model outperforms CRF and BiLSTM-CRF on most languages, dropping down to 81.8% on the Italian dataset, comparable to the best baseline models, when trained on judgements and evaluated on laws. Unsurprisingly, the models’ performance in the zero-shot experiment is almost always lower than the performance on the subset they were trained on. This gap can be explained by the large difference of writing and formatting styles between judgements and laws, with the transformer model being the best at generalizing knowledge between the two subsets. We further hypothesize that it was easier for the models to generalize their knowledge to different domains, when being trained on judgements, than when being trained on laws, resulting in higher scores on unseen data. One factor here might be that legal text in judgements contain a higher variety of different sentence structures, while laws usually reuse the same structures.

The CRF and BiLSTM-CRF model showcase especially poor performance on the Spanish dataset when trained on laws and evaluated on judgements, with scores down to 43.4% and 54.3%. We hypothe-

size that both models possess a worse ability to generalize to different domains compared to transformer models.

6.3 MULTILINGUAL MODELS

The performance of our multilingual models trained on laws and judgements is reported in the lower section of Table 3. Each multilingual model was trained on all languages except Portuguese. A more detailed report including multilingual models trained on all laws or all judgements separately is available in Appendix i.

The multilingual models clearly outperform the baseline models by a large margin, with F₁-scores up to 99.2%. Both the BiLSTM-CRF and transformer models perform very well, with transformer performing slightly better on judgements and BiLSTM-CRF on laws. The CRF model is close behind the other two, mostly reaching scores in the higher nineties. Comparing the performance of the multilingual models to the monolingual models, showcases that there is no loss of performance when training on a much larger dataset, with multilingual models performing comparably or in case of the transformer and BiLSTM-CRF model even better than the monolingual models on each respective language.

Figure 9: Mean performance comparison of baseline (green) and trained models (violet) on multilingual legal text and a zero-shot experiment

6.4 ZERO-SHOT EXPERIMENT ON PORTUGUESE DATA

As an additional, more challenging experiment, we evaluated the multilingual models from the previous section on unseen Portuguese data and compared them to the baseline. An overview can be found in Fig. 9. More detailed results are shown in Table 3, showcasing the difference between the judgements and laws compared to the baseline. A full report, including Recall and Precision, is shown in Appendix i.

For judgements, the performance is still adequate, reaching F1-scores between 90.2% and 93.6%, comparable to the reported performance on user-generated content (Read et al., 2012), outperforming most of the baseline models. However, for laws only the transformer model reaches the lower nineties, while for CRF and BiLSTM-CRF, the scores drop to 78.6% and 73.2% respectively, comparable to our usual baselines values. We hypothesize that one part of the good cross-lingual transfer performance of the transformer model stems from the fact that all of our chosen languages originate from the same language family. Another part might stem from the fact that larger pre-trained transformer models are publicly available and that these models are pre-trained on many languages, including Portuguese.

The difference between laws and judgements could be explained by the increased difficulty of the writing and formatting style used in Portuguese law texts, also indicated by the lower than usual Portuguese baseline performance. Another reason for the lowered performance of the BiLSTM-CRF could be the lack of Portuguese word embeddings used in training, as we extracted the embeddings from our training data. For future research, it would be interesting to see whether adding Portuguese word embeddings or using even larger, multilingual embedding vocabularies during training would increase the performance of the BiLSTM-CRF models. A potential avenue for further improving the transformer models might be the utilization of larger pre-trained models for fine-tuning on the SBD task such as XLM-RoBERTa (Conneau et al., 2020), which reports significant improvements on cross-lingual transfer tasks compared to BERT based models.

6.5 INFERENCE TIME

Table 5: Mean inference time in minutes (min), seconds (s), milliseconds (ms) for each multilingual model to predict the entire dataset of ~130000 sentences and one sentence, measured on a GPU and CPU

Model	full dataset (~130000 sentences)		One sentence	
	CPU	GPU	CPU	GPU
CRF	11 min 57 sec	-	~5.37 ms	-
BiLSTM-CRF	10 min 6 sec	9 min 23 sec	~4.54 ms	~4.21 ms
transformer	34 min 26 sec	9 min 18 sec	~15.47 ms	~4.18 ms

The inference times of our multilingual models trained on both laws and judgements are reported in Table 5. We measured the inference time twice on a GPU (NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 TI) and CPU (Intel Core i5-8600K CPU @ 3.60GHz) and showcase the average. We do not report the standard deviation, since there were no significant

outliers. We see large improvements when measuring inference time on a GPU, especially for the transformer model. Note here, that CRF is a model utilizing sequential operations, rather than batch operations; thus it does not benefit from being evaluated on a GPU.

Considering the results presented in Subsections 6.2 and 6.3, inference times and ease of use, a recommendation for the multilingual transformer model can be made for most cases, as long as a GPU is available for inference. For language specific tasks or tasks requiring longer input texts, we recommend the CRF models for the respective language, although they have a longer setup time compared to the BiLSTM-CRF and transformer model. The transformer models can be found on [HuggingFace](#) and our CRF and BiLSTM-CRF models as well as the code on [GitHub](#).

6.6 ERROR ANALYSIS

We inspected random samples, 8 judgements and 20 law articles, predicted by the multilingual transformer model for the zero-shot experiment on Portuguese texts. We selected the multilingual transformer following our recommendation in section 6.5, and the Portuguese dataset, as the model already performed very well on the other datasets.

Standard sentences boundaries are rarely missed and the model performs adequately in that regard; yet, we identified a few sources of common mistakes. We discuss examples with |T| and |P| indicating true and predicted sentence boundaries, respectively. Many errors stem from citations and parentheses as shown in the example below:

- (Bittar, Carlos Alberto. |P| Direito de autor. |P| Rio de Janeiro: Forense Universitária, 2001, p. 143) |T| |P|

In this example, we have a citation sentence with periods being wrongly predicted as sentence boundaries inside the citation.

Another source of errors are datafields and headlines, as there is often little indication e.g., a sentence-terminating character, for the model to recognize it as such:

1. RELATOR: MINISTRO SIDNEI BENETI |T|
2. ACÓRDÃO |T|

In both examples, the model did not predict a sentence boundary at the end of the sequence. The errors showcased in all of the examples above mainly stem from our particularly defined sentence structures (Section 3.1.1) as well as the challenging nature of the legal SBD task.

Another set of errors were caused by the different formatting styles and words used in the Portuguese language, unknown to the model, such as:

1. A Turma, por unanimidade, deu provimento ao recurso especial, nos termos do voto do(a) Sr(a). |P| Ministro(a) Relator(a).
|T| |P|
2. Exmos. |P| Desembargadores MAURÍCIO PESSOA (Presidente),
CLAUDIO GODOY E GRAVA BRAZIL. |T| |P|

In (1), we have the abbreviation "Sr(a)", which the model did not recognise as such, thus marking the period as a sentence boundary. A similar mistake is shown in (2), with the abbreviation "Exmos" .

6.7 LIMITATIONS

Due to the language skills of our annotator, we only annotated data from two language groups (Germanic and Italic). Therefore, our languages have high lexical overlap, making cross-lingual transfer comparatively easy. Future work may investigate legal text from additional diverse language groups to build even more robust systems.

The annotator is a native German speaker, with intermediate French language skills. Due to the similarity of Italian, Spanish, and Portuguese to French, and because the SBD task is largely structural, the annotations were possible. However, having the annotations performed by a native speaker in the respective languages may further increase annotation quality. On the other hand, having one annotator (as done in our case) annotate the entire dataset, enables more consistency across languages.

Because of financial limitations, we performed the annotations using only one annotator. Having a second annotator validate the annotations may further increase annotation quality.

Augmenting the qualitative error analysis from Section 6.6 quantitatively may provide more concrete and actionable evidence for improving the systems further. For this, a more detailed annotation of the sentence type would be helpful, so we can compute statistics over the sentences to get quantitative results of the sentence types performing worst.

CONCLUSION & OUTLOOK

7.1 ANSWERS TO THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- RQ1: *What is the performance of existing SBD systems on legal data in French, Italian, Spanish, English and German?* It is subpar in all tested languages, lower than reported scores by Read et al. (2012) on user-generated content, showcasing that SBD is not solved in the legal domain.
- RQ2: *To what extent can we improve upon this performance by training mono- and multilingual models based on CRF, BiLSTM-CRF and transformers?* All monolingual models reach F1-scores in the higher nineties on all tested languages, demonstrating state-of-the-art performance, comparable to reported scores on news articles (Read et al., 2012). The multilingual models perform comparably to the monolingual models, illustrating the possibility of training with larger datasets. The transformer model showcases the best cross-domain knowledge transfer compared to the CRF and BiLSTM-CRF models.
- RQ3: *What is the performance of the multilingual models on previously unseen Portuguese legal text i.e. a zero-shot experiment?* The transformer models performs adequately on the judgements and laws subsets, reaching F1-scores in the lower nineties, demonstrating the best cross-lingual transfer, while the CRF and BiLSTM-CRF models perform decently around 90% on judgements, but drop down to baseline values on the laws, most likely requiring additional optimization.

7.2 CONCLUSION

In this work, we have curated and publicly released a diverse legal dataset consisting of over 130'000 annotated sentences in 6 languages for the community to perform further research in the legal domain. Using this dataset, we showed that existing SBD methods perform poorly on multilingual legal data, at most reaching F1-scores in the low nineties. We trained and evaluated mono- and multilingual CRF, BiLSTM-CRF and transformer models, achieving binary F1-scores in the higher nineties on our dataset, demonstrating state-of-the art performance. For a more challenging task, we tested our multilingual models in a zero-shot experiment on unseen Portuguese data, with the transformer model reaching scores in the lower nineties, outper-

forming the baseline trained on Portuguese texts as well as the CRF and BiLSTM-CRF models by a large margin. We publicly release these models and the code for further use and research in the community.

7.3 FUTURE WORK

There are several directions for future work. Further improvement in all model performance might be achieved by pre-processing the input text more, e.g. replacing newlines with spaces, special characters with more widely used equivalent characters e.g., double quotes (“”) with single quotes ("). Another avenue for improvement, especially for the multilingual CRF and BiLSTM-CRF models, could be a more in-depth hyperparameter optimization, adapting them to the dataset, as we did not invest a large amount of time to perfect the parameters. For the transformer models, improvements likely could be achieved by using larger pre-trained models such as BERT (Devlin et al., 2019) or models more suited for cross-lingual transfer tasks such as XLM-RoBERTa (Conneau et al., 2020).

The effect of augmenting the dataset with legal texts from additional languages as well as adding documents from different sources such privacy policies or terms of service on the performance of the multilingual models, especially in the zero-shot scenario, should lead to interesting results. Labeling the sentence spans with their type sentence structure such as "Citation" (Section 3.1.1) for training, instead of just a single label, might have an interesting effect on model performance.

Finally, following the hypothesis that the good cross-lingual transfer shown in the zero-shot experiment stems in part from the fact that all of our languages originated from the same language family (Section 6), it could be of interest whether the good cross-lingual transfer holds up for languages from a different family such as Hungarian.

Part I

APPENDIX

DATASET SOURCES

Wipolex

Jus.unitn.it

SJP

MLP

Glaser, Moser, and Matthes (2021)

Savelka et al. (2017)

CRF FEATURE REPRESENTATION

A sample representation of "en" in the sequence "C'est en outre ...":

```
{
  'bias': 1.0, 'o:lowercase': 'en', 'o:lower': True, 'o:upper': False,
  'o:numeric': False, 'o:special': 'No', 'o:sign': 'cc', 'o:length': 2,
  'o:BOS': False, 'o:EOS': False, '-1:BOS': False, '-1:special': 'S',
  '-1:lowercase': '', '-1:length': 1, '-1:sign': 'S', '-1:lower': False,
  '-1:upper': False, '-1:number': False, '-1:space': True, '-2:BOS': False,
  '-2:special': 'No', '-2:lowercase': 'est', '-2:length': 3,
  '-2:sign': 'ccc', '-2:lower': True, '-2:upper': False, '-2:number': False,
  '-2:space': False, '-3:BOS': False, '-3:special': 'Abbr',
  '-3:lowercase': '', '-3:length': 1, '-3:sign': 'S', '-3:lower': False,
  '-3:upper': False, '-3:number': False, '-3:space': False, '-4:BOS': True,
  '-4:special': 'No', '-4:lowercase': 'c', '-4:length': 1, '-4:sign': 'C',
  '+1:EOS': False, '+1:special': 'S', '+1:lowercase': '', '+1:length': 1,
  '+1:sign': 'S', '+1:lower': False, '+1:upper': False, '+1:number': False,
  '+1:space': True, '+2:EOS': True, '+2:special': 'No',
  '+2:lowercase': 'outre', '+2:length': 5, '+2:sign': 'ccccc',
  '+2:lower': True, '+2:upper': False, '+2:number': False, '+2:space': False
}
```

PERFORMANCE OF BASELINE MODELS

In Tables 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 we report the performance of all baseline models for French, Spanish, Italian, English, German and Portuguese respectively.

PERFORMANCE OF TRAINED MONOLINGUAL MODELS

In Tables 12, 14, 13, 15 and 16 we report the performance of all trained monolingual models for French, Spanish, Italian, English and German respectively.

Table 6: Performance of baseline models on the French dataset

Type Model	Judgements			Laws		
	F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CoreNLP	74.7	68.8	81.7	76.7	98.5	62.9
NLTK	72.5	65.6	80.9	75.8	94.8	63.1
NLTK-train	82.9	87.2	79.0	75.8	95.1	63.1
Spacy	86.6	83.6	89.9	67.2	61.3	74.9
Stanza	81.9	81.3	82.5	81.0	80.7	81.4

Table 7: Performance of baseline models on the Spanish dataset

Type Model	Judgements			Laws		
	F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CoreNLP	71.4	82.5	63.5	89.0	98.6	81.2
NLTK	70.2	82.3	61.5	89.2	99.4	81.0
NLTK-train	72.1	89.7	60.4	81.6	99.9	69.1
Spacy	60.0	79.6	48.4	70.3	79.9	62.9
Stanza	83.2	81.2	85.5	90.2	97.7	84.0

Table 8: Performance of baseline models on the Italian dataset

Type Model	Judgements			Laws		
	F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CoreNLP	79.8	81.8	78.0	75.6	91.6	64.6
NLTK	72.3	63.0	85.7	66.3	67.2	66.0
NLTK-train	84.8	86.4	83.2	77.5	94.1	66.0
Spacy	73.9	63.7	88.5	73.7	79.5	69.0
Stanza	85.7	86.0	85.6	87.4	92.2	83.4

Table 9: Performance of baseline models on the English dataset

Type Model	Judgements		
	F1	Precision	Recall
CoreNLP	81.7	81.5	82.0
NLTK	77.2	72.2	83.1
NLTK-train	84.9	87.4	82.6
Spacy	79.7	89.0	72.3
Stanza	92.3	95.0	89.8

Table 10: Performance of baseline models on the German dataset

Model	Type	Judgements			Laws		
		F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CoreNLP		69.0	63.4	75.6	64.0	66.8	61.4
NLTK		72.3	69.2	75.7	73.8	92.4	61.4
NLTK-train		74.2	73.0	75.3	73.5	91.5	61.4
Spacy		87.5	81.8	94.1	67.0	59.8	76.1
Stanza		72.6	69.1	76.5	64.7	65.4	64.0

Table 11: Performance of baseline models on the Portuguese dataset

Model	Type	Judgements			Laws		
		F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CoreNLP		-	-	-	-	-	-
NLTK		64.9	74.3	58.2	57.0	69.3	50.6
NLTK-train		71.7	93.4	58.4	64.3	97.1	49.9
Spacy		59.0	52.5	67.4	77.7	90.1	68.9
Stanza		88.6	87.6	89.9	73.4	90.4	62.2

Table 12: Mean (\pm std) performance of trained models on French dataset

Model	Trained on	Judgements			Laws		
		F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CRF	Judg.	97.94	97.38	98.50	73.18	88.09	62.62
	Laws	78.45	84.25	73.40	98.84	99.54	98.15
	Laws + Judg.	98.83	98.24	99.42	99.18	99.75	98.64
BiLSTM-CRF	Judg.	97.27 \pm 0.27	96.80 \pm 0.51	97.74 \pm 0.57	56.65 \pm 2.99	63.66 \pm 2.06	51.78 \pm 6.36
	Laws	66.07 \pm 4.22	70.71 \pm 13.56	63.70 \pm 5.43	97.94 \pm 0.20	98.47 \pm 0.25	97.40 \pm 0.27
	Laws + Judg.	97.03 \pm 0.43	96.45 \pm 0.67	97.62 \pm 0.46	98.07 \pm 0.13	98.84 \pm 0.30	97.32 \pm 0.14
transformer	Judg.	98.24 \pm 0.13	97.39 \pm 0.26	99.10 \pm 0.06	84.73 \pm 1.21	93.44 \pm 0.48	77.67 \pm 2.15
	Laws	92.45 \pm 0.47	96.43 \pm 0.68	88.79 \pm 0.96	97.58 \pm 0.40	98.00 \pm 0.77	97.18 \pm 0.11
	Laws + Judg.	98.36 \pm 0.08	97.78 \pm 0.10	98.95 \pm 0.13	98.23 \pm 0.22	99.17 \pm 0.40	97.31 \pm 0.12

Table 13: Mean (\pm std) performance of trained models on Italian dataset

Model	Trained on	Judgements			Laws		
		F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CRF	Judg.	98.50	98.60	98.41	95.64	96.42	94.97
	Laws	88.59	87.92	89.48	99.61	99.52	99.70
	Laws + Judg.	98.28	98.41	98.14	99.52	99.50	99.54
BiLSTM-CRF	Judg.	95.92 \pm 0.27	96.44 \pm 0.56	95.41 \pm 0.63	71.32 \pm 2.21	85.90 \pm 8.23	61.60 \pm 3.68
	Laws	74.08 \pm 1.21	87.32 \pm 3.03	65.12 \pm 3.14	98.36 \pm 0.25	99.20 \pm 0.20	97.53 \pm 0.47
	Laws + Judg.	96.21 \pm 0.19	97.36 \pm 0.67	95.11 \pm 0.66	98.17 \pm 0.13	99.08 \pm 0.15	97.28 \pm 0.31
transformer	Judg.	97.84 \pm 0.18	98.17 \pm 0.28	97.52 \pm 0.20	81.82 \pm 0.85	76.88 \pm 1.07	87.65 \pm 2.13
	Laws	89.41 \pm 0.69	95.35 \pm 0.48	84.20 \pm 1.53	98.81 \pm 0.49	99.33 \pm 0.51	98.29 \pm 0.48
	Laws + Judg.	97.08 \pm 0.25	97.29 \pm 0.33	96.88 \pm 0.21	99.11 \pm 0.09	99.61 \pm 0.09	98.62 \pm 0.09

Table 14: Mean (\pm std) performance of trained models on Spanish dataset

Model	Trained on	Judgements			Laws		
		F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CRF	Judg.	96.98	98.61	95.40	98.32	98.91	97.76
	Laws	54.34	65.84	46.44	99.64	99.52	99.76
	Laws + Judg.	97.02	98.34	95.76	99.48	99.36	99.60
BiLSTM-CRF	Judg.	94.65 \pm 0.54	97.61 \pm 0.53	91.92 1.02	92.06 \pm 0.92	97.01 \pm 1.74	87.61 \pm 0.91
	Laws	43.43 \pm 6.81	54.63 \pm 4.73	37.73 10.14	98.69 \pm 0.19	99.27 \pm 0.16	98.11 \pm 0.36
	Laws + Judg.	95.62 \pm 0.49	97.53 \pm 0.65	93.79 0.46	98.94 \pm 0.38	99.21 \pm 0.39	98.66 \pm 0.38
transformer	Judg.	96.86 \pm 0.17	97.80 \pm 0.16	95.94 0.25	96.92 \pm 0.36	97.86 \pm 0.19	96.01 \pm 0.62
	Laws	89.48 \pm 0.57	91.63 \pm 0.75	87.43 0.65	97.15 \pm 3.73	97.55 \pm 3.78	96.74 \pm 3.68
	Laws + Judg.	97.32 \pm 0.09	98.12 \pm 0.02	96.54 0.19	98.95 \pm 0.07	99.31 \pm 0.06	98.60 \pm 0.15

Table 15: Mean (\pm std) performance of trained models on English dataset

Model	Trained on	Judgements		
		F1	Precision	Recall
CRF	Judg.	98.76	98.84	98.69
BiLSTM-CRF	Judg.	97.34 \pm 0.40	97.18 \pm 0.56	97.51 \pm 0.38
transformer	Judg.	97.96 \pm 0.08	97.84 \pm 0.14	98.08 \pm 0.13

Table 16: Mean (\pm std) performance of trained models on German dataset

Model	Trained on	Judgements			Laws		
		F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CRF	Judg.	97.77	98.12	97.43	76.51	96.50	63.38
	Laws	75.82	78.68	73.16	97.67	97.88	97.47
	Laws + Judg.	97.17	97.52	96.83	97.22	97.88	96.56
BiLSTM-CRF	Judg.	97.01 \pm 0.27	97.74 \pm 0.39	96.29 \pm 0.69	76.86 \pm 0.43	95.44 \pm 0.49	64.34 \pm 0.66
	Laws	71.90 \pm 2.55	73.33 \pm 5.00	71.06 \pm 5.74	97.33 \pm 0.33	97.72 \pm 0.46	96.94 \pm 0.30
	Laws + Judg.	97.16 \pm 0.20	97.36 \pm 0.44	96.97 \pm 0.57	97.56 \pm 0.16	98.34 \pm 0.16	96.78 \pm 0.23
transformer	Judg.	97.96 \pm 0.23	98.08 \pm 0.13	97.84 \pm 0.35	87.18 \pm 0.43	96.05 \pm 0.33	79.82 \pm 0.56
	Laws	89.40 \pm 0.51	93.04 \pm 0.98	86.04 \pm 1.05	97.44 \pm 0.05	97.37 \pm 0.12	97.51 \pm 0.12
	Laws + Judg.	98.34 \pm 0.13	98.07 \pm 0.09	98.60 \pm 0.19	97.47 \pm 0.16	97.65 \pm 0.20	97.30 \pm 0.25

Table 17: Mean (\pm std) performance of multilingual models on all languages

Language		French		Spanish		Italian		English	German	
Model	Type Trained on	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Laws	Judg.	Judg.	Laws
CRF	Judg.	97.4	93.3	95.7	96.5	97.9	77.3	95.7	95.0	72.1
	Laws	89.8	98.3	63.6	98.4	84.1	98.3	69.2	75.2	94.0
	Laws + Jug	97.8	98.1	94.8	98.9	97.3	97.7	95.1	95.2	91.6
BiLSTM-CRF	Judg.	97.9 \pm 0.2	94.0 \pm 0.8	97.0 \pm 0.2	96.2 \pm 0.7	97.7 \pm 0.2	87.6 \pm 0.8	95.6 \pm 0.5	96.8 \pm 0.2	76.5 \pm 1.0
	Laws	77.8 \pm 0.9	98.4 \pm 0.2	52.5 \pm 2.6	99.0 \pm 0.2	82.4 \pm 1.7	98.9 \pm 0.2	56.4 \pm 1.9	74.2 \pm 2.3	97.7 \pm 0.3
	Laws + Jug	97.6 \pm 0.3	98.5 \pm 0.2	97.3 \pm 0.1	99.3 \pm 0.2	97.8 \pm 0.1	99.2 \pm 0.1	95.4 \pm 0.3	97.2 \pm 0.2	97.5 \pm 0.5
transformer	Judg.	98.3 \pm 0.0	93.5 \pm 1.1	97.8 \pm 0.1	97.7 \pm 0.2	98.3 \pm 0.1	85.5 \pm 0.6	97.0 \pm 0.1	98.4 \pm 0.1	86.7 \pm 0.3
	Laws	94.9 \pm 0.4	98.3 \pm 0.2	90.3 \pm 1.2	99.0 \pm 0.1	92.6 \pm 0.4	99.1 \pm 0.0	88.9 \pm 0.8	89.3 \pm 0.9	97.3 \pm 0.1
	Laws + Jug	98.3 \pm 0.1	98.1 \pm 0.2	97.8 \pm 0.1	99.0 \pm 0.0	98.3 \pm 0.1	99.1 \pm 0.1	97.0 \pm 0.1	92.9 \pm 0.2	97.6 \pm 0.1

Table 18: Mean (\pm std) performance of multilingual models on unseen Portuguese texts

Type		Judgements			Laws		
Model	Trained on	F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
CRF	Judg.	92.2	94.4	90.2	76.5	84.4	71.1
	Laws	56.3	59.3	55.5	69.7	72.2	70.2
	Laws + Judg.	90.2	91.7	88.8	78.6	88.2	71.5
BiLSTM-CRF	Judg.	92.5 \pm 1.5	93.9 \pm 0.8	91.2 \pm 3.0	78.5 \pm 4.0	93.4 \pm 2.3	68.5 \pm 5.8
	Laws	46.1 \pm 1.5	58.2 \pm 5.8	38.8 \pm 4.3	76.2 \pm 3.2	91.7 \pm 3.8	66.2 \pm 4.9
	Laws + Judg.	93.0 \pm 0.6	96.0 \pm 0.8	90.4 \pm 1.3	73.2 \pm 3.3	97.2 \pm 0.7	61.2 \pm 4.1
transformer	Judg.	93.7 \pm 0.3	93.5 \pm 0.3	93.8 \pm 0.4	92.8 \pm 0.2	93.7 \pm 0.7	91.9 \pm 0.6
	Laws	84.5 \pm 0.9	91.1 \pm 0.3	78.8 \pm 1.8	91.7 \pm 0.4	93.5 \pm 0.5	90.2 \pm 0.9
	Laws + Judg.	93.6 \pm 0.3	93.6 \pm 0.4	93.5 \pm 0.2	91.3 \pm 1.1	94.2 \pm 0.5	88.8 \pm 1.7

PERFORMANCE OF TRAINED MULTILINGUAL MODELS

In Tables 17 and 18 we report the performance of all multilingual models on all languages and their zero-shot performance on Portuguese legal text.

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